

A BESPOKE SELF-HEALING AGENT FOR RESIDUAL STRENGTH IMPROVEMENT OF BIO-INSPIRED COMPOSITES.

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SUMMARY

Self-repair via embedded liquid filled hollow fibres provides a biomimetic approach to increase damage resistance in FRPs. A bespoke epoxy based self-healing agent is proposed and its ability to restore mechanical properties in CFRP is investigated. The healing efficiency is measured as a recovery of the residual compression strength after impact.

Keywords: self-healing agent, multifunctional composites, damage tolerance, strength recovery, crack arresting.

INTRODUCTION

Composite materials subjected to low energy impact events usually result in large areas of complex damage within the laminate which are very difficult to detect and characterise. Much effort has been invested in trying to improve both their intrinsic damage tolerance behaviour by chemical modification of the matrix and optimising design parameters to be employed in order to reduce their susceptibility. An innovative approach to the problem of improving damage tolerance is to impart a multifunctional behaviour to the laminate where damage *can be sensed and repaired autonomously* by the composite material. The idea, inspired by the natural ability of “living materials” to self-heal any internal damage would allow a ‘step-change’ in damage tolerance philosophy. Such an approach would allow designers to impose less punitive restrictions on design allowables, because an autonomous fail-safe system is able to ensure that internal damage has been repaired and/or stress fields readjusted.

The possibility of imparting an autonomous repair mechanism has been investigated for many different materials such as asphalt, concrete, coatings, and polymer composite materials [1]. A self-repair concept, comprising an integrated mechanism able to restore the loss in mechanical properties caused by damage, was first proposed by Dry [2]. The idea of embedding glass tubes in fibre reinforced polymers has also been considered by Motuku [3] and refined by Bleay [4]. The latter proposed a smart repair technique by the use of μm scale capillaries. The hollow glass fibres can be filled with a one-part or two-part resin system and after damage occurrence, a crack would break the HGF containers enabling the ‘bleeding’ self-repair mechanism. A parallel branch of research, White et al. [5] has proven the possibility of fully autonomously healing cracks in

polymer matrices by means of the use of a coupled microencapsulated dicyclopentadiene monomer/Grubb's catalyst as a healing system. Despite the successful demonstration of high efficiencies of the self-healing system on polymers, the application to fibre reinforced polymers has not been so successful [6, 7]. Work by Yin *et al.* [8, 9] followed a similar approach with a microencapsulated epoxy monomer dispersed within a glass/epoxy FRP in conjunction with a dissolved latent imidazole hardener. Fracture toughness testing using double cantilever beam specimens indicated healing efficiencies of ~70% for 30 wt% capsules and 2 wt% latent hardener. However, such capsule loadings saw a marked degradation in tensile stiffness and strength of the FRP. Also, the need for a substantial increase in temperature (130°C for 1 hour) means a marked deviation from autonomous healing.

Bond's group has demonstrated that resin filled hollow glass fibres can be nested between the reinforcing fibres, minimising any disruptive effects [10, 11]. If a two component epoxy resin is used as the healing agent within the hollow glass fibres, a recovery of up to 89% of flexural strength after impact [11] and 92% of the compression after impact strength [12, 13] has been demonstrated in carbon reinforced plastic (CFRP). Whilst this process diverges slightly from the original aim of achieving fully autonomous self-healing, the use of a pre-mixed resin and elevated temperature to accelerate the process is an attempt to demonstrate that a delivery system comprising embedded hollow fibres can provide an optimal ratio of healing efficiency to structural disruption with current technologies.

The formulation of a novel self-healing agent which allows a fully autonomous repair of mechanical properties represents an urgently needed step forward in the field of self-healing composite materials. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to evaluate and down select the most effective of several different specially formulated epoxy self-healing agents (SHA) with respect to autonomous recovery of compression strength after impact (CAI). The down selection process first evaluated the physical and chemical characteristics of several candidate two-part epoxy formulations. The most promising candidate was then taken forward to demonstrate its effectiveness at recovering compression strength of a CFRP composite laminate after a low velocity impact event.

EXPERIMENTAL

Previous research has shown that commercially available epoxies enable restoration of mechanical properties after exposure to a 120°C curing cycle [11, 12, 13]. In order to obtain autonomous (ambient temperature) self-healing, a wide range of bespoke epoxy based SHAs were formulated for the present study. Each of these potential SHAs was optimised with respect to different critical properties, such as low viscosity and tolerance to non-stoichiometric mixing, whilst exhibiting excellent mechanical performance when cured [14].

An assessment of the ease of infiltration time of different SHA formulations into typical small orifices (i.e. cracks) was assessed by using layers of HGF, 20 mm x 250 mm,

Figure 1 Infiltration time assessment for the different self healing agents

vertically connected to a vacuum line at one end, while the other end was exposed to a SHA filled reservoir, Figure 1. A measure was then made of the relative time necessary to infiltrate a 200 mm length of hollow glass fibre.

A Perkin Elmer Diamond Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC) was used to characterise the cure characteristics of each formulation. The degree and rate of reactivity is expected to be robust under ambient conditions. To simulate exposure of a SHA to in-flight conditions (e.g. $-55\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) in an aerospace application, each formulation was investigated to determine whether it possessed an ability to rapidly return to a low viscosity liquid state and undertake a reaction upon restoration to ambient conditions. The DSC characterisation followed a five stage thermal cycle:

- Ramp from ambient temperature to $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Hold 5 minutes at $50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
- Cool down to $-5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$
- Ramp from $-50\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ to ambient at $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$

This thermal analysis provided an indication of the epoxy monomer's phase change response under representative aerospace environmental conditions.

The reactivity of different SHA formulations has been assessed by determining the gel point following mixing. The gel point of a polymer undergoing cure, is defined as the instant at which elastic and storage modulus achieve the same value in a dynamical mechanical analysis. However, as the exact gel time is not important, an alternative rudimentary method of determining relative reactivity between different formulations is proposed.

The reactive components are mixed in a 7ml vial until clear. The formulation is then rotated between horizontal and vertical orientations every hour for the first 2-4 hours, increasing to every ten minutes when the viscosity became noticeably higher. The gel time is taken as the instant at which the healing agent ceases flowing from the vertical position to the horizontal within sixty seconds.

From these findings, an optimal SHA formulation was selected and assessed as an autonomous healing agent for the recovery of compression strength after impact (CAI) in CFRP panels

Figure 2 Sequence of experiments carried out for an autonomous healing to occur

A 210 mm x 210 mm CFRP panel capable with and without self-healing functionality was manufactured with four embedded layers of hollow glass fibres [i.e. 8 ply (-45°/HGF/90°/HGF/45°/0°)_s]. A CFRP currently used for high performance structural aerospace applications (Cytec M21-T700G 268 gsm) was used as the host material. The selected SHA was then pre-mixed and infused into the exposed hollow fibres with a vacuum assist technique. When the hollow fibres were fully infiltrated, a 5J energy low velocity impact was immediately undertaken using an instrumented drop-weight tester (Instron Dynatup 9250HV) (Figure 2). After 24 hours the healed panel was cut into smaller 89mm x 55mm coupons (four replicates per panel type) and tested for residual compression strength in accordance with a modified ASTM D7137 [12, 15]. The residual strength after impact was also evaluated in non self-healing panels, (i.e. without SHA infiltration) as control assessment for this geometry.

RESULTS

The thermal analyses show that the epoxy monomer *triglycidylether of para-aminophenol* (TGPAP) subjected to a temperature profile between ambient and 50°C at a rate of 10°C/min does not show any primary transition in this temperature range. When cooling from ambient to -50°C at 10°C/min a crystallisation peak was found at -38°C for the epoxy monomer TGPAP. This simple thermal analysis is not able to fully characterise the kinetics of crystallisation, however, the results show that TGPAP has low susceptibility to solidification and as such is suitable as an SHA in low temperature environments i.e. aerospace. It is also interesting to note that when epoxy monomers are mixed with a reactive diluent the tendency for crystallisation diminishes. This phenomenon can be explained by the increased entropic contribution to the free energy of crystallisation thereby diminishing the driving force for the solidification.

The time necessary for each bespoke epoxy SHA formulation (TGPAP monomer + reactive diluent + amine hardener) to reach the gel point is reported in Figure 3. The time of reaction was investigated as function of the hardener and diluent contents and, thereby, considered different stoichiometric mixtures. When the hardener content was reduced to a minimum of 10% the reaction was very sluggish and the gelation process required more than 24 hours.

Figure 3 Time of reaction in logarithmic scale for different bespoke epoxy formulations

Conversely, when hardener content was as much as 20%, the measured gel time was around 5 hours. However, the most reactive SHA formulations (high hardener and medium diluent content) reached a gel state within two hours.

A tension exists between the rate of reaction of an SHA and the time for infiltration into any damage as cure progresses (i.e. increase in viscosity). Thus, studies were made of the time for epoxy monomer infiltration and the influence of an added reactive diluent in relation to extent of reaction progression. This evaluation is conservative in terms of time as the further addition of curing agent (hardener) reduces initial viscosity.

Table 1 HGF infiltration time for diluent and epoxy monomer mixtures

Formulation	Infiltration time
Epoxy 0	>45 Minutes
Epoxy 10%	30 Minutes
Epoxy 20%	20 Minutes
Epoxy 40%	10 Minutes
Epoxy 50%	5 Minutes

Table 1 shows that the infiltration process is slower for low dilution of epoxy monomer. Following full consideration of all chemical and physical properties, a 50% diluted epoxy monomer (TGPAP) pre-mixed with appropriate amine hardener, was selected for CAI mechanical testing. This choice ensured that HGF infiltration, impact testing and damage infusion could all take place before SHA gelation and would provide an indication of the SHA effectiveness.

Each test coupon was subject to a 5J low velocity impact before being allowed to heal under ambient conditions for 24 hours. The results from the CAI testing indicate a significant (~30%) increase in the residual compression strength, Figure 4.

Figure 4 Residual strength after 5J impact of self-healing and non self-healing CFRP specimens

However, the presence of a relatively high number of ply interfaces containing HGF within the CFRP laminate (i.e. 4 layers in 8 pre-preg plies) created a significantly disruptive effect with a 38% strength reduction compared to the panels with no HGF. Work is ongoing to further optimise the self-healing architecture to ensure any degradation in laminate performance is minimised whilst healing function is maximised.

CONCLUSION

A bespoke SHA based on a mixture of epoxy monomer, reactive diluent and amine hardener was used to demonstrate a quasi-autonomous self-healing process. The residual compressive strength after 5J low velocity impact indicates a 30 % recovery following the healing process. Further optimisation of the delivery system (HGF) location and distribution within the laminate is needed to move towards the complete recovery of mechanical properties and reduce any detrimental effects on the host laminate.

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REFERENCES

1. Self Healing Materials: an alternative to 20 centuries of materials science. Ed. S. van der Zwaag, 2007. Springer Dordrecht, ISBN 978-1-4020-6249-0

2. Dry C. 1992. Passive Tunable Fibers and Matrices. *International Journal of Modern Physics B*, 6(15-16): 2763-2771.
3. Motuku M, Vaidya UK & Janowski GM. 1999. *Smart Materials & Structures*, 8(5): 623-638.
4. Bleay SM, Loader CB, Hawyes VJ, Humberstone L & Curtis PT. 2001. *Composites: Part A*. 32(12): 1767-1776.
5. White SR, Sottos NR, Geubelle PH, Moore JS, Kessler MR, Sriram SR, Brown EN & Viswanathan S. 2001. *Nature*, 409(6822): 794-797.
6. Kessler MR & White SR. 2001. *Composites: Part A*. 32(5): 683-699.
7. Kessler MR, Sottos NR & White SR. 2003. *Composites: Part A*. 34(8): 743-753.
8. Yin T, Rong MZ, Zhang MQ & Yang GC. 2007. *Composites Science & Technology* 67(2), 201.
9. Yin T, Zhou L, Rong MZ & Zhang MQ. 2008. *Smart Mater. Struct.* 17, 8.
10. Bond IP, Trask RS, Williams GJ, Williams HR. 2008. *MRS Bulletin – Theme: Bio-Inspired Self-Cleaning and Self-Healing*. 33(8), 770-774.
11. Trask RS & Bond IP. 2006. *Smart Materials & Structures*, 15(3), 704-710.
12. Williams GJ, Trask RS & Bond IP. 2007. *Composites: Part A*. 38(6). 1525-1532.
13. Williams GJ, Bond IP & Trask RS. 2008; *Composites: Part A*. On-line June 2008. (doi:10.1016/j.compositesa.2008.05.021).
14. Imperiale VA & Bond IP. AIAA 2008-1740, Proc. 49th AIAA /ASME/ ASCE/ AHS/ ASC, 7 - 10 April 2008, Schaumburg, IL, USA.
15. ASTM International, D 7137/D 7137M05